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Nationalism: Global Problems Need Global Answers

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Abstract: Today we are living in a fragmented world. We, the modern Homo sapiens have built barriers around us in the name of safety, security, state, country and nationalism. The nationalism is born to offer solutions to the existential realities of the mother earth. The problems are such as nuclear, technological and ecological. The act of the modern man is endangering the survival of the species including the human species. Therefore, I have taken the article “Nationalism: Global problems need global answers” as the primary source which is written by Yuval Noah Harari in the book *21 lessons for the 21st century*. Throughout this article, I will explore on the question Does returning to nationalism offer real solutions to the problems that induced the nationalism to be born? I will explore the areas of how the modern world deforms the mother earth for their selfish motives, what could be the real substantial solution for the

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cry of the mother earth with the summary of the Harari's article, my personal critical evaluation and applying it into the present scenario.

Keywords: *Homo sapiens*, Nationalism, Nuclear, Technological, Ecological, Isolationism Cosmotheandric spirituality and interconnectivity

Introduction

There once lived a miller with his daughter. When the miller was at work all day turning grain into flour, he loved nothing more than to think up tall tales to amaze people.

One day the King came to town. He heard the miller talking about his daughter. The miller was saying that his daughter was the most amazing girl in their village, if not in all the land.

“You there!” said the King. “What is so amazing about your daughter?”

The father bowed. He said, “Your Majesty, my daughter is so clever that she can spin straw into gold!”

“Spin straw into gold?” said the King. “That is amazing! She must come to my palace. I will put her to the test!”

“But I mean...” said the miller. He wished he had not told the King such a thing! But now it was too late.

So the miller's daughter had to go to the King's palace at once. The King took her to a room piled with straw from floor to ceiling. He pointed to the spinning wheel in the middle of the room. He said, "Now get to work! If by morning you have not spun this straw into gold, you will die!"

The King slammed the door and locked it behind him. The girl was all alone.

For the life of her, she did not know what to do. She had no idea how to spin straw into gold! "What will I do?" she called out to the air. "No one can do such a thing!"

Just then, an odd little man stood before her. "Did I hear you say, 'no one'?" he said.

"What?" said the girl, shocked. "Where did you come from?"

"Never mind that!" said the imp. "What matters is I can save your life. For a price, of course."

"You can spin straw into gold?" said the girl. "What kind of price do you have in mind?" She did not know if she should trust this stranger.

"What you give must be important to you," said the imp. "How about that necklace?"

The girl thought, "Indeed, my necklace is very dear to me. But not as much as my freedom." So she said to the imp, "Very well. If by morning you can turn this room full of straw into gold, this necklace is yours."

The world today is following just like that king who was greedier. We can drink the milk from the breast but not blood. The globalized world today is sucking the blood of the mother earth in the name of technology and

The little man got to work. Very busy he was, all night long. Whirr, whirr, whirr, until morning. By then, not one piece of straw was left in the room – all of it was turned into piles of pure gold thread!

“You did it!” said the girl.

“Of course I did!” snapped the imp. “Now hand over that necklace!”

“A deal is a deal,” said the girl. She took off her necklace and gave it to him. And he was gone.

When the King stepped into the room, he was very glad. “Look at that!” he said, running the gold thread through his fingers. “Pure gold!”

“Yes,” said the girl. “Now if you please, sir. I’d like to go home now.”

“Not so fast!” said the King. “I will have my servants bring new straw to fill up a room larger than this one. You will stay there tonight. Beware – by morning all the straw must be spun into gold. If you care about your life!” (Pandikattu, 2002).

The world today is following just like that king who was greedier. We can drink the milk from the breast but not blood. The globalized world today is sucking the blood of the mother earth in the name of technology and development. Humankind’s life longs for happiness, serenity, peace and love in the world. This happiness, serenity, peace and love are attainable when everyone is together irrespective of all the conditions. The Homo sapiens for millions of years lived and died in this way but modern humankind constrained them with limitations on the basics of nation, state or country. There are various factors which induced to this nationalistic life that we see later. But the question, we have to arise is Does returning

to the nationalism or nationalistic life offer real solutions to the factors that induced to the nationalism? When we look at our life of nations, states, districts and provinces from multiple angles, we arrive at a conclusion that other creatures such as birds, animals, and reptiles are more independent than human kind. They can explore the whole world; they can venture into any corner of the world. But, do you think that humankind can do as same as they go on venturing and exploring. The genuine answer is no. Returning to nationalism has not offered real solutions to the challenges that induced people towards the nationalistic and individualistic life and more over I would say that nationalistic is not naturalistic but individualistic and destructive.

What is Nationalism?

Nationalism is an idea and movement that promotes the interests of a particular nation, especially with the aim of gaining and maintaining the nation's sovereignty over its homeland. The nation is a territorial community of nativity. One is born into a nation. The significance attributed to this biological fact of birth into the historically evolving, territorial structure of the cultural community of the nation is why the nation is one among a number of forms of kinship. It differs from other forms of kinship such as the family because of the centrality of territory. It differs from other territorial societies such as a tribe, city-state, or various 'ethnic groups' not merely by the greater extent of its territory, but also because of its relatively uniform culture that provides stability, that is, continuation over time. I feel that this definition itself is meant for the human beings. This definition for nationalism is not inclusive. They worry about the Liberty, Equality and fraternity of the human beings but never bother about the other species. We need to break this attitude first and foremost to bring a balanced earth where everyone is safe including all the species. The problem, Harari warns, starts when benign

patriotism morphs into chauvinistic ultra-nationalism. Instead of believing that my nation is *unique*, which is true of all nations, I might begin feeling that my nation is *supreme*.

Inducements for Nationalistic Life: Harari's Basic Insights

Our life is at stake in this millennium because we are deforming the face of our mother earth in the name of development. The natural calamities are the signs that show that our mother earth is in anguish, sorrow and she is constantly weeping for the enormous harm we have done to her. Today the ecology is more inclusive and everybody feels the pinch of it since in one or other way they are affected by the eco problems. As human beings have symptoms for each sickness, Mother Earth also has some symptoms to show us that she is sick. The symptoms are erratic climatic changes, melting of the polar ice caps, rising of the ocean levels by over two feet, inundation of coastal cities and towns, a rise in the frequency and vehemence of droughts, storms, rains, floods, tidal waves, nuclear and technological challenges. It isn't a coincidence that skepticism about climate change tends to be the preserve of the nationalist right, says Harari. You rarely see left-wing socialists tweet that climate change is a Chinese

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hoax. When there is no rational answer, but only a global answer to the problem of global warming, some nationalist politicians prefer to believe the problem does not exist. So these ecological, nuclear and technological problems are the factors that induce the people to return to and to be constrained by nation and nationalism.

Because, the scary factors such as ecological, nuclear and teleological cannot be solved very easily unless a group of people come together under one wing as a nation, state or country as for Harrai. We see in the book that Take, for example, the ancient tribes that lived along the

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Nile River thousands of years ago. The river was their lifeblood. It watered their fields and carried their commerce. But it was an unpredictable ally. Too little rain – and people starved to death; too much rain – and the river overflowed its banks and destroyed entire villages. No tribe could solve this problem by itself, because each tribe commanded only a small section of the river and could mobilize no more than a few hundred laborers. Only a common effort to build huge dams and dig hundreds of kilometers of canals could hope to restrain and harness the mighty river. This was one of the reasons why the tribes gradually coalesced into a single nation that had the power to build dams and canals, regulate the flow of the river, build grain reserves for lean years, and establish a countrywide system of transport and communication. This is how gradually people started the nationalistic life.

a. The Nuclear Challenge

Humankind successfully rose to the nuclear challenge. Russia and the USA have recently embarked on a new nuclear arms race, developing novel doomsday machines that threaten to undo the hard-won gains of the last decades and bring us back

to the brink of nuclear annihilation. It was extremely difficult to construct the internationalist regime that prevented nuclear war and safeguarded global peace. No doubt we need to adapt this regime to the changing conditions of the world. But abandoning this regime altogether and reverting to nationalist power politics would be an irresponsible gamble. True, in the nineteenth century countries played the nationalist game without destroying human civilization. But that was in the pre-Hiroshima era. As long as humans know how to enrich uranium and plutonium, their survival depends on privileging the prevention of nuclear war over the interests of any particular nation. Zealous nationalists who cry ‘our country first!’ should ask themselves whether their country by itself, without a robust system of international cooperation, can protect the world – or even itself – from nuclear destruction.

b. The Ecological Challenge

Humans are destabilizing the global biosphere on multiple fronts. We are taking more and more resources out of the environment, while pumping back into it enormous quantities of waste and poison, thereby changing the composition of the soil, the water and the atmosphere. We are hardly even aware of the myriad ways in which we disrupt the delicate ecological balance that has been shaped over millions of years. Modern industrial farming is based on artificially fertilizing the fields with plenty of phosphorus which caused the plants to become extinct. Whole ecosystem is degraded. If we continue with our present course it will cause not just the annihilation of a large percentage of all life forms, but it might also sap the foundations of human civilization. In order to avoid such things, the nationalism and nationalistic isolationism

comes in. Nationalist isolationism is probably even more dangerous in the context of climate change than of nuclear war.

c. The Technological Challenge

The third existential threat of the twenty-first century is technological disruption. The nuclear war and climate change threaten only the physical survival of humankind, disruptive technologies might change the very nature of humanity, and are therefore entangled with humans' deepest ethical and religious beliefs. While everyone agrees that we should avoid nuclear war and ecological meltdown, people have widely different opinions about using bioengineering which shows that the technology became inseparable and part and parcel of the human existence. The technological revolutions of the twenty-first century should really be understood in cosmic terms since everyone in the world interconnected through technology. Therefore, in order to make wise choices about the future of life we need to go way beyond the nationalist viewpoint and look at things from a global or even a cosmic perspective.

Jesus the Cosmic Liberator

Jesus in his life and teaching very much emphasized on the togetherness and community living with loving each other as brothers and sisters. He didn't give way for the division among peoples. But, today everyone is divided on the basic of social structures. Jesus learns and draws profound insights from nature such as God's unconditional love, whereby he sends rain on the good and bad alike. His parables were drawn from nature and he taught using insights from nature, using imageries like the sun and the rain, salt and light (Mt 5:13-14), the birds of the air (Mt 6:26), the lilies of the field (Mt 6:28, Lk 12:27), the grass (Mt 6:30), grapes (Mt 7:16), good trees producing good fruit (Mt 7:17-18), the seed, the rocks, and the foxes (Lk 9:58), the mustard seed (Mt 13:31-32), the sowing

of seed (Mt 13:4-9, 18, 23), vine (Jn 15:1-17, Mk 12:1-12, Mt 21:33-44, Lk 20:9-19), the lost sheep (Lk 15:4-7) and shepherds (Jn 10:1-15). He is the Good Shepherd (Jn 10:11, Mk 6:30-44) who brings abundant life (Jn 10:10). In his preaching he identified himself with water (Jn 4:13-14), bread (Jn 6:48) and light (Jn 8:12). In and through such imageries he taught the people to have a loving disposition towards nature. For him the Father's love is for all that he has created, even the lilies and he says that God provides for them all (Lk 12:24).

My Personal Take

Today we are living in a fragmented world. We, the modern Homo sapiens, have built barriers around us in the name of safety, security, state, country and nationalism. Chaos and confusions are taking place in the name of nationalism. This very nationalistic thinking crates a vibrant selfishness among the people of particular nation who don't even consider the neighbour people of other nation as equal with them. This superior complex reality instilled in them is very precarious and easily it helps them to take violence on other nations, people and nature. Just remember the war of the USA over Iran. The US wanted to take the oil wealth of Iran and therefore, on the name of war it fulfilled. This is how the ecology is being destroyed on the condition of nationalism. They are now an independent nation with nationalism and

Each of these three problems – nuclear war, ecological collapse and technological disruption – is enough to threaten the future of human civilization. But taken together, they add up to an unprecedented existential crisis, especially because they are likely to reinforce and

ideology but the question is does returning to nationalism offer real solutions to the facts that induced the nationalism to be born? The genuine answer is no.

Each of these three problems – nuclear war, ecological collapse and technological disruption – is enough to threaten the future of human civilization. But taken together, they add up to an unprecedented existential crisis, especially because they are likely to reinforce and compound one another. At present our mother earth lost her originality and original face. She is dominated by the climatic chaos the climatic chaos are overconsumption of natural recourses, air pollution, deforestation pesticides, artificial fertilizers, developmental destruction, globalization, water scarcity, water pollution, global warming, vanishing species, overpopulation, genetically modified food, noise pollution and ozone depletion. The ecological crisis is endangering the very survival of the human species together with all other life forms within this millennium. Within the next 100 years the average temperature of the planet will rise by 4.5 degree Celsius and this rise in temperature is a purely man-made phenomenon due to the uncontrolled emission of poisonous gases from the industrialized nations. Due to this rise in temperature of the planet there will be erratic climatic changes, melting of the polar ice caps, rising of the ocean levels by over two feet, inundation of coastal cities and towns, a rise in the frequency and vehemence of droughts, storms, rains, floods, and tidal waves. This time calls for immediate and concerted action from all concerned. Though the human race has been vandalizing the resources of our planet for more than a century for the selfish needs of a consumerist society, Mother Earth is constantly struggling to protect herself from such vandalism. She cries in anguish at the destruction of the environment threatening the very survival of all living beings including the human species. What is the cause for the degradation and

deformation of the mother earth? The three principal and important causes are nuclear crisis, technological crisis and ecological crisis. Nationalism is born to offer real solutions to this existential ecological crisis of our mother earth. As raised in the beginning, does returning to nationalism offer real solutions to the existential problem? The genuine answer could be no. why because a nation cannot eradicate all these problems alone. It needs the cooperation and collaboration of all the nations since all of us are travelling in the same boat called mother earth. Every nation should conscientize the people that human species is one among the species on earth and there is interconnectivity between all the species.

The interconnectivity is being broken by the nuclear, technological and ecological crisis. The technological gadgets which are connected through the radiation and magnetic waves are engendering the survival of the birds. Many birds vanished due to this electromagnetic wave and radiation. This technological problem breaks the interconnectivity that is

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present in all the species. When the interconnectivity is broken, then the species are vanishing and the continuous vanishing of the species would cause destruction of human survival on earth. For instance, Trees would live without human beings' presence but human beings cannot live without trees. Einstein says "if the bees disappeared off the surface of the globe then man would only have four years of life left. No more bees, no more pollination, no more

plants, no more animals and no more man”. And like trees many other creatures can live without human beings but we cannot continue our existence without those creatures. This shows the interconnectedness. Therefore, don’t harm nature; don’t deform the face of the mother earth. Mother earth can fulfil the need but not your greed. When we conscientize people like this through education, then we can give the medication to the wounded mother earth.

Contextualization

There is something fundamentally wrong with the world we live in. Added to it, there is also something basically wrong with the humans who live in this world. So however hard humans try to improve the world, there is really no scope for a better future. (Pandikattu, 2002). There is a tremendous transformation stuck between the homo sapiens of the past and present. The homo sapiens of the past were more of leavers and the homo sapiens of the present are more of takers.

Difference between Leavers and Takers

The Leavers Are More Awakened, Vigilant and Cosmotheandric in Nature

Why do I say that the leavers are more awaken and vigilant? It is because; they were aware and conscious about their past, present and the future. With this awareness, they approached each and everything on the earth and as a result they were very friendly with the humans, nature and divine. There was a Cosmotheandric world view.

No Superiority Complex over Other Species

The leavers were so concerned about the upcoming species including human beings. The interesting fact is that they didn't have a superior mind set over the other creatures. Therefore, they loved and left us the creatures without missing any species that was created on this earth. Today the question is: Can we leave everything to the next generation that we see, experience and enjoy on this earth? The genuine answer is no. That is why the present generation is called takers.

Takers Are Destroyers and Utilitarianist in Nature

The takers are destroyers. They do all the nonsense they want to do against nature to accumulate money and wealth. They follow utilitarianism. They don't bother about the implications of their acts. They do whatever they want provided it must be happy and useful for them. They don't care about the negative implications of their harm that they have done to nature.

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Dominion Over Other Creatures

The takers are dominant in nature. They dominate the whole creation by destroying them. They feel that they are the superiors of the whole creation. In order to prove it substantially, they misquote the biblical verse also. The ninety percentages of people today are takers. This ninety percent people are cruel towards the ecologists, eco warriors and eco activists.

If you are counting on rising oceans, dwindling food supplies and mass migrations to divert our attention from algorithms and genes, think again. As the ecological crisis deepens, the development of high-risk, high-gain technologies will probably only accelerate.

Is the Leaver Life Possible Anymore?

The sad part is that it is almost impossible to revert to a Hunter, Gatherer way of life without significant, perhaps catastrophic societal collapse and rebuilding. It might be possible in remote parts of Africa, Alaska, outback Australia, or the Amazon jungle. But our world is just not set up for that way of life anymore. There are too many people to feed. We need agriculture to survive. Without it, our planet's natural food resources would be stripped so thoroughly that natural recovery before human extinction would be next to impossible.

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Reversing the Eventual Destruction of Our Planet

Everybody should adopt the life style of the leavers. Why do I say that everyone should become leavers is that just look at the daily life of the people. They are some home fed the attitude of the takers. As long as the attitude of the takers lives with us we cannot save nature, we cannot love nature.

We can follow the Cosmotheandric Spirituality by the following means:

- In recovering the lost dignity and honour of Mother Earth we need to adopt a Cosmotheandric spirituality taking into consideration the intimate link between the cosmos, the divine, and the human race. The Infinite manifestation of the Divine is the Cosmos and Mother Earth emerges from the cosmos to give life to the human race. This spirituality makes the affirmation that every being is created by God. This spirituality invites us to live a life of harmony and peace with oneself, others, cosmos and God.
- We could stop using fossil fuels. Right now we are making the Middle East rich by buying their oil because it is convenient and easy. We need to rebuild our electrical grid so that it is modern, and can utilize solar infrastructure. Then we need to work hard to decrease our dependence on fossil fuels in favor of renewable energy technology.
- We could work toward establishing a societal norm that calls for smaller families. Gone are the days of high infant mortality rates and family farms that require many hands to operate. Families no longer need more children than parents. Two children in a family is enough.
- We could make electric cars the standard instead of the exception. At one time California required all manufacturers that sold cars in the state to have at least one electric car. It brought about some great innovations and vehicles. But the oil industry squashed this.

Conclusion

Today we are standing at the crossroads. Nationalism didn't offer real solutions to the cry of mother earth. Today many disciplines are born out of nationalism which are more dangerous. They are liberalization, globalization and privatization. On these grounds, our natural resources are destroyed. In order to save mother earth, we need to have Cosmotheandric spirituality. If we continue deforming our mother earth, then we will meet the tremendous destruction caused by the eco problems. Through our education, we need to provoke the conscience of humanity to radical action for a sustainable and harmonious environment for the very survival of all life forms on this planet.

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